

Comparative Study of Traditional Machine Learning, Deep Learning, and Transformer Models for Fake News Detection with Explainability Analysis

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Abstract

This research presents a methodical evaluation of traditional machine learning, deep learning, and transformer-based models for classifying fake news. The dataset used is a large-scale benchmark dataset - the WELFake dataset. Apart from the model comparison, contrast of only the title is used v/s when the title and text are combined as the input data to better understand the impact of text length and representation on each model performance. The findings indicate that TF-IDF with Naive Bayes can still act as a competitive baseline. And though combining title with text does increase the accuracy and F1 scores per model, supplying only text results in good scores with complex models. The transformer-based model has the highest performance. Further deep-dive into model transparency using LIME and SHAP to explore interpretability while examining token-based contributions for classification decisions. Overall, the results illustrate that models rely on evidence-based tokens when predicting real news consistently across models, perhaps because certain words or patterns act as key signals for credibility. trade-offs between predictive performance and interpretability in automated fake news detection systems.

Keywords: Fake News Detection, Natural language Processing, Machine Learning, Transformer Models, Model Interpretability, LIME, SHAP

1. Introduction

Large-scale dissemination of information is now enabled due to the rapid expansion of digital media. This has amplified the spread of fake news, leading to serious social consequences such as political polarization, misinformation during public health crises and lack of trust in credible journalism. [1] ; Automated fake news detection systems based on machine learning and deep learning have therefore become an important research focus [2].

Most existing studies emphasise accuracy as the primary objective to calculate performance [3]. And because transformer-based architecture out-performs other models in classification [4] we overlook the importance of transparency in decision-making. In socially sensitive avenues the ability to interpret why a piece of content is classified fake or real is necessary to foster trust and ensure accountability. [5] Therefore, Interpretability is a central requirement for responsible deployment of such systems. [6]

Despite the growing interest in explainable artificial intelligence [7], few works systematically compare interpretability across different model families or examine how text representation influences both performance and explanation quality. In this study, these gaps are addressed by evaluating classical machine learning, neural network, and transformer-based models on the WELFake dataset using both title-only and combined title-text inputs. Tools like LIME and SHAP

are applied to further token-level explanations and compare the patterns across models [8]. Even though transformer-based models achieve the highest overall performance, TF-IDF with Naive Bayes is still a good baseline for such text classification tasks. [9] The findings highlight the key trade-off between predictive accuracy and Interpretability, providing insights for the design of more transparent and reliable fake news detection systems.

2. Contribution Statement

The main contributions of this work are summarized as follows:

1. We conduct a comparative evaluation of machine learning and deep learning models for fake news detection, analyzing their effectiveness in distinguishing between real and misleading news content.
2. We investigate linguistic patterns in misinformation using natural language processing techniques, highlighting features that contribute to model predictions.
3. We perform a post-hoc interpretability analysis using LIME and SHAP, providing insights into how different models make predictions and identifying the most influential textual features.
4. We discuss limitations and potential future research directions for building more robust fake news detection systems.

3. Related Work

Traditionally fake news detection was extensively studied using lexical and statistical features. Early Machine learning approaches employed bag-of-words or vector representations like TF-IDF combined with models like Naive Bayes and Logistical Regression [10, 11]. These methods provide us with a strong baseline performance and still remain very relevant and competitive due to their computational efficiency and high interpretability. Several studies have results where linear models trained with TF-IDF vector representations perform similar to more complex neural architectures on large scale datasets, especially if the linguistic patterns are not present evidently [12].

Deep learning models like RNN, LSTM and BiLSTM capture semantic and contextual and contextual dependencies in news text [13]. These models provide improved performance over traditional machine learning models because of their long range dependencies and sequential data information. Additionally, BiLSTM models incorporated both forward and backwards sequences into its modelling [14]. However, LSTM-models are very sensitive to parameters, input length, and data imbalance, which can result in unstable predictions and performance collapse in certain settings [13, 15].

Today, transformer-based models like BERT achieve state-of-the-art results in fake news classification tasks (16). BERT captures deep contextual relationships between words without relying on customised features. It leverages large scale pretraining embeddings and self-attention mechanisms. Several studies have demonstrated how fine-tuning BERT models outperform traditional machine learning and neural network architectures significantly when it comes to benchmark fake news datasets [6, 17]. However, transformer based models increase computational complexity and reduce transparency, motivating further research into their interpretability.

Explainable AI (XAI) methods have been increasingly applied to natural language processing tasks. Tools like LIME and SHAP explain individual predictions by providing word-level factors [18, 19]. These methods have been applied for various NLP tasks like sentiment analysis, hate-speech

detection, and fake news classification. It provides insights into important features and potential biases. However, most existing studies study the interpretability techniques with respect to a model or a dataset, rather than conducting systematic comparisons across multiple models and input representations.

In summary, existing studies focus on predictive accuracy, with limited exploration of interpretability, especially how it differs in models with different architectures, be it traditional ML techniques, neural nets or transformer models. There has been few studies which investigate the combined effects of textual representations (title-only versus full text) and model explainability. The present research is driven because of this gap. It integrates performance evaluation with LIME and SHAP-based analysis to explore both effectiveness and transparency in fake news detection.

4. Dataset & Methodology

4.1 Dataset

For data, WELFake dataset [20] is used for fake news detection. It is a large-scale benchmark corpus with approximately 71,537 news articles. The dataset has two classes : real and fake, with an almost balanced distribution with 51% real news articles and 49% as fake. Each instance contains the news title and the corresponding article. This becomes important when experimenting with numerous input configurations.

This study uses the WELFake dataset, a large-scale benchmark corpus for fake news detection consisting of approximately 71,537 news articles. The dataset has two classes: real with a 51% distribution and fake with 49%, which is nearly balanced. Each row contains the news title and its article text, making it possible to experiment with different inputs. Due to the size of the dataset we can use it for both traditional machine learning and deep learning models and make possible comparisons.

We constructed two different inputs : (1) `processed_title`, which is only the headline, and (2) combination of title with text. This design allows us to further investigate how well the models can perform with shorter vs longer textual inputs. We performed vectorization on the inputs before feeding it to the models

4.2 Data Preprocessing

The input for all models underwent a similar preprocessing pipeline to reduce noise and make them standardised. The text was converted to lowercase, punctuation, special characters and numbers were removed. Further the input text was vectorized or tokenized using methods like TF-IDF [21]. In order to preserve linguistic patterns stop words were not removed.

For models Like Naive Bayes and feed forward neural network models, the processed text was transformed using TF-IDF whereas for sequential models like LSTMs and BiLSTMs the input is converted to tokenized and padded sequences [22]. And for transformer based models, the bert-base-uncased tokenizer is used [16]. It applied WordPiece tokenization and includes special classification tokens.

4.3 Models

Five different model families were implemented and compared in this study:

- Naive Bayes (NB): A probabilistic classifier trained on TF-IDF feature representations, serving as a strong and interpretable baseline.
- Logistic Regression: Another supervised machine learning algorithm which uses the sigmoid function to classify real and fake news. The input data is preprocessed the same way and vectorized using TF-IDF.
- Neural Network (NN): A feed-forward neural network using TF-IDF features as input to examine whether nonlinear decision boundaries improve performance over NB [13].
- LSTM: A recurrent neural network which uses sequential data as input to take care of vanishing gradient problems. The input data is tokenized and padded [22].
- BiLSTM: Special LSTM structure which captures information from past and future by processing the data both forward and backward [14].
- BERT: A transformer-based model which leverages bidirectionality of self attention mechanisms. It is pretrained using bert-base-uncased architecture, fine-tuned for binary classification for highly efficient, parallelized language understanding [16].

This diverse model set allows comparison across traditional machine learning, deep learning, and transformer-based approaches while keeping preprocessing and evaluation protocols consistent.

4.4 Training Setup

The dataset is split into 80% training and 20% testing. Training data is further split into training and validation for hyperparameter tuning and early stopping. To make sure that the comparison is fair, every model is trained using identical splits. Also, training is conducted with the same random seed to ensure reproducibility.

After the model, confusion matrix and classification reports are generated. Accuracy and Micro-F1 score are the metrics used to assess model effectiveness. Depending on the context for the detection of fake news, false positives and false negatives can have different social implications.

In order to avoid overfitting, early stopping is employed for deep learning models and transformer based models on validation loss. Also, class weights were tested during modeling to check if the metrics can be improved to compensate for the minor class imbalance. Furthermore, hyperparameter tuning is performed on learning rate, batch size, sequence length, etc based on validation performance.

4.5 Explainability Methods

Interpretability is explored using LIME and SHAP to enhance model transparency [18, 24] These methods are very useful as they produce token-level scores based on their importance. It highlights which words or phrases might contribute towards the model's decision making for a particular prediction. For a select text sample explanations are generated and compared to observe how different architectures rely on different textual clues. This helps us in a systematic understanding of trade-offs between model performance and interpretability.

Explanations were generated for selected test samples across all model types to compare how different architectures rely on textual cues. For deep learning models and transformer based models

predictive performance increases but it becomes impossible to interpret them. This helps in a systematic examination of the interpretability of the classifiers.

5. Experiments & Results

This section presents the experimental evaluation of the models for fake news classification. We further explore how each model performs with different input representations: title-only and title + text. Every model is trained and tested with the same data splits and evaluation metrics to make sure that the comparison is fair. Performance is checked on accuracy and Micro F1 Score, which provide complementary insights into overall correctness and class-wise balance.

5.1 Quantitative Results

Table 1 showcases the performance across all models with both input representations. The purpose is to demonstrate the effectiveness of these models and how their architecture can improve the performance of the models or becomes a disadvantage

Table 1: Model Performance on WELFake Dataset

Model	Input	Accuracy	F1 Score
Naive Bayes	Title	0.77	0.76
Naive Bayes	Title + Text	0.87	0.87
Logistic Regression	Title	0.80	0.81
Logistic Regression	Title + Text	0.95	0.95
Neural Network	Title	0.90	0.90
Neural Network	Title + Text	0.96	0.96
LSTM	Title	0.51	0.34
LSTM	Title + Text	0.97	0.965
BiLSTM	Title	0.91	0.915
BiLSTM	Title + Text	0.97	0.97
BERT	Title	0.93	0.935
BERT	Title + Text	0.99	0.99

Figure 1: LIME explanation showing the contribution of token "video" toward the Real class prediction.

Figure 2: Comparison of model explanations across architectures for the same news sample tested on a small sample with 7 tokens.

Figure 2.a : Naive Bayes LIME Interpretability

Figure 2.b : Feed Forward Neural Network LIME Interpretability

Figure 2.c : Bidirectional-LSTM LIME Interpretability

Figure 3. Example showing tokenization artifact (“deplorabletrump”) receiving negligible importance weight.

Table 2 : Token contribution comparison table

Token\ Model	Naive Bayes	Neural Network	Bi-LSTM
guilty	+0.03 (Fake)	+0.33 (Real)	+0.31 (Real)
trail	+0.16 (Fake)	+0.21 (Real)	+0.35 (Real)
deplorabletrump	0.00 (Real)	0.00 (Fake)	0.00 (Fake)

Interpretability analysis reveals several patterns across models.

1. Tokens associated with evidence or reporting, such as “*video*”, frequently contribute toward the Real class, suggesting that references to verifiable media may act as credibility signals [Figure 1].
2. Predictions for the same sample vary across model architectures. Simpler models such as Naive Bayes assign relatively low probability to the target class (0.36), whereas more complex models such as Bi-LSTM predict the same class with substantially higher confidence (0.87). This suggests that neural architectures capture stronger contextual patterns in the text compared to traditional probabilistic models [Figure 2].
3. The importance of individual tokens varies across models. For instance, the token *guilty* contributes positively toward the Fake class in Naive Bayes (0.03), while neural architectures assign the same token a stronger contribution toward the Real class (0.33 in the neural network and 0.31 in Bi-LSTM). This indicates that more complex models interpret token semantics differently by incorporating contextual signals [Figure 2].
4. While Naive Bayes assigns relatively small contributions to individual tokens, neural architectures produce larger attribution weights for key words such as *trial* and *guilty*. This suggests that sequence-based models can capture richer contextual patterns, resulting in stronger feature importance and higher predictive confidence [Figure 2].
5. Finally, tokenization artifacts such as “*deplorabletrump*” highlight potential preprocessing limitations, as these combined tokens receive negligible importance scores while still influencing classification outcomes [Figure 3].

5.2 Performance Comparison Across Models

Transformer architecture-BERT model performed the best for both title and title + text combination. In fact it performed with a F1 score of 0.99 for both, which shows how it can extract maximum contextual semantics and long range dependencies even with short inputs. Finetuning of the pretrained model was done on the WELFake dataset. This suggests that the headline alone might contain sufficient discriminative information for fake news classification. This might show that even in low-resource scenarios we might get a good performance.

However, classical models with combination with TF-IDF vectorisation of the input provided good baseline results. Both Naive Bayes and logistic regression performed robustly. With a simple neural network performed significantly better. These findings demonstrate that lexical features when carefully engineered can be highly effective as competent baseline models when detecting fake news and can rival more complex black box architectures under certain conditions. For example, Logistic regression with title and text as input outperforms Feed Forward Neural Network with only title as input.

5.3 Failure of LSTM and Model Stability

A particular interesting result is the poor performance of the LSTM model when it is trained only on the headlines. The model produces a F1 score of 34%. Upon further investigation, it is revealed that the model actually collapsed and was simply classifying the entire test data as the majority class. This suggests that the LSTM model becomes very unstable if it is provided with short text sequences. It is unable to extract sufficient contextual information for learning meaningful patterns.

However, the LSTM model performs significantly better when the input is the combination of title and text. It lags a little behind compared to Bi-LSTM crediting its bi-directional nature compared to the uni-directionality of the LSTM model. These results emphasize the sensitivity of recurrent models to input length and highlight the importance of sufficient textual context for sequence-based learning.

5.4 Title-Only vs Title + Text Representation

Logistic Regression shows noticeably improved performance when provided with additional context. Specifically, when trained using both the news headline and the full article text, the model performs substantially better compared to using the title alone. When trained only on titles, the model's performance increases by approximately 3%, whereas incorporating the full text leads to an improvement of about 8%.

A similar pattern is observed across all evaluated models. In every case, model performance improves when both the headline and article content are used as input rather than relying solely on the title. For deep learning and transformer-based architectures, the improvement ranges between 5–6%, while traditional machine learning models benefit more significantly from the additional context, with performance gains of approximately 10% for Naive Bayes and 15% for Logistic Regression.

These results suggest that longer textual inputs provide richer semantic information that can enhance model predictions. However, the findings also indicate that using only the headline can

still provide reasonably informative signals for fake news detection. Title-only inputs significantly reduce computational cost and inference time, albeit at the expense of slightly lower predictive accuracy. The choice between these input representations therefore depends on the specific application context and whether the trade-off between efficiency and performance is acceptable, particularly when powerful pretrained language models are employed.

5.5 Interpretability Analysis

Apart from predictive performance, the models are further compared by examining their interpretability using LIME and SHAP explanations. These techniques identify the contribution of individual tokens toward a particular prediction by assigning token-level importance scores, allowing a quantitative analysis of the model's decision process.

For TF-IDF based models such as Naive Bayes and Logistic Regression, the explanations were largely dominated by explicit lexical cues. Words associated with sensational or emotionally charged language contributed strongly toward the predicted class [Table 2]. In contrast, neural architectures such as feed-forward neural networks and Bi-LSTM models showed different attribution patterns, where the importance of certain tokens shifted depending on the broader context. For example, tokens such as *“guilty”* contributed toward the Fake class in the Naive Bayes model but shifted toward the Real class in neural models, indicating that more complex architectures interpret the same lexical cues differently [Figure 2, Table 2]

Transformer-based models such as BERT relied less on isolated keywords and more on contextual word relationships and phrase-level semantics [Table 1]. Although these models achieved higher predictive accuracy, their internal decision processes were less transparent compared to simpler models. This reduced transparency can pose challenges in high-stakes domains such as misinformation detection, where understanding the reasoning behind a prediction is important. Therefore, post-hoc interpretability techniques such as LIME and SHAP play an important role in analyzing and validating model behavior.

5.6 Summary of Key Findings

1. Transformer-based architectures such as BERT consistently outperform all other models for both input configurations (title-only and title + text), achieving the highest accuracy and Micro-F1 scores.
2. TF-IDF with Naive Bayes remains a strong baseline, demonstrating that classical machine learning approaches can still achieve competitive performance while remaining computationally inexpensive.
3. Sequential models such as LSTMs show instability when trained on short text inputs, often collapsing toward majority-class predictions when insufficient contextual information is provided.
4. Across models, combining title and article text generally improves performance, but title-only representations still provide competitive results, particularly when using powerful pretrained language models.
5. Interpretability analysis using LIME and SHAP reveals that models rely on different types of textual cues. Traditional models tend to rely on explicit lexical indicators such as

emotionally charged or polarized terms, while more complex architectures leverage broader contextual patterns.

6. Additionally, interpretability results show that token importance and prediction confidence vary significantly across model architectures. Simpler models often assign lower confidence to predictions based on limited lexical evidence, while deeper architectures capture richer contextual relationships and produce more confident predictions for the same sample.

The above findings highlight the trade-offs between model performance and computational efficiency, and interpretability in automated fake news detection systems.

6. Explainability Analysis

For fake news detection, research often focuses primarily on a model's predictive performance. However, it is equally important to understand why a model makes a particular decision in order to build trustworthy and transparent systems [2]. To address this, we conducted an explainability analysis using two widely adopted post-hoc interpretation techniques: LIME (Local Interpretable Model-agnostic Explanations) and SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations).

Classical machine learning models and deep learning architectures were interpreted using LIME, which provides local explanations by approximating the model's behavior around individual predictions [18]. For the transformer-based model BERT, we applied SHAP, which estimates the contribution of each token to the final prediction using Shapley values derived from cooperative game theory [19].

6.1 LIME Explanations for TF-IDF Based Models

For traditional models like Naive Bayes and Logistic Regression as well as for Feed Forward Neural Network the classifiers were trained on TF-IDF features [21]. After modeling, LIME was used as a tool for token-level explanations for individual predictions. Thus, providing us with words and phrases that strongly contribute towards the classifiers decision towards real or fake news [18].

It was interesting to note that tokens like "bloody", "graphic", and "diplorabletrump" seem to push the classifiers towards fake news. Words like these are often present in sensational or clickbait-style headlines. And are also observed in misinformation content. Alternatively, neutral tone words like "video", "supporters", and "confirmed" contribute towards real news predictions. Perhaps such results are due to the lexical nature of TF-IDF and these words can be noted as providing a sense of 'evidence' giving the news more credibility as it is real.

When focusing on human-centered analysis LIME explanations seem quite intuitive and easy to interpret. However, LIME depends on the local perturbations which means the explanations can change across runs and may even be sensitive to small changes in the input text. Despite this drawback, LIME is beneficial in providing insight into how specific keywords are prioritised by machine learning models while classifying.

6.2 SHAP Explanations for the BERT Model

SHAP was applied to interpret the transformer-based classifier - BERT to compute a token-level contribution score for each prediction. Unlike LIME, SHAP is grounded in cooperative game theory. It calculates the marginal contribution of each token to the final prediction across all possible furniture subsets [19]. Therefore, the results are more stable and theoretically justified explanations.

The SHAP explorations showcase that BERT does not only rely on keywords alone but also on the broader contextual patterns across input sequences. For example, compared to individual words, the phrases with casual relationships, emotional framing, and syntactic structure were often given more importance [16].

Also, compared to LIME, SHAP explanations were more consistent across repeated runs; however, they require higher computational cost due to their complexity [5].

6.3 Comparative Analysis of LIME and SHAP

There are important differences between LIME and SHAP when it comes to interpretability and practical usability. For example, LIME is particularly effective for feature-based models such as Naive Bayes and Logistical Regression as it produces sparse and human readable explanations [18]. This is helpful as they emphasize important keywords and provide immediate insight into lexical patterns associated with misinformation.

In contrast, SHAP is helpful with transformer architecture models because it provides deeper insight into contextual decision-making. Although SHAP may seem less intuitive at first it better captures the relation between words and phrases [19]. Although SHAP has the advantage of analyzing complex structures such as BERT, it also comes with the cost of increased computation time and implementation complexity compared to LIME [5].

In conclusion, SHAP provides a more principled and stable explanation framework for deep contextual models whereas LIME can be considered a lightweight and intuitive tool.

6.4 Implications for Trust and Transparency

The interpretability explorations highlighted an important tradeoff between model complexity and transparency. Traditional machine learning models may miss subtle semantic cues but always provide easily interpretable decisions, while transformer - based architectures may have reduced transparency but achieve a higher predictive performance [5].

These interpretability tools help identify potential biases, detect spurious correlations and improve user trust in automated fake news detection systems by exposing token-level contributions [2]. Such transparency is essential in high stakes domains such as misinformation analysis because it enables responsible deployment and human oversight [10].

7. Discussion

Looking at the performance of classical machine learning, deep learning and transformer based models for fake news classification, there is a clear difference in the experimental result. Highest F1 score and accuracy was achieved by the transformer based model BERT for both title-only and title+text inputs, highlighting its ability to look beyond surface-level keywords and capture contextual semantics [15, 16]

In contrast, LSTM models collapsed towards predicting the majority class and exhibited unstable behaviour when trained on title-only input. This suggests that sequential models are not very effective for sparse or short-text classification tasks as they are highly sensitive to input length [22]. Interestingly, simple model structures combined with TF-IDF like Naive Bayes and Logistic Regression still remain relevant and competitive when compared to complex structures [21].

Experiments comparing the performance of models when trained with just the title versus when input consisted of title and text combined there was a slight increase in performance for deep learning and transformer based models but a significantly larger increase in classical machine learning models. Depending on the scenario sometimes only the title might be enough for discriminatory information. This makes it possible for light weight fake news detection systems where computational resources or full text might not be possible.

While exploring interpretability, noteworthy differences between machine learning models workings when classifying a class. LIME explanations highlighted sensational tokens or emotionally charged tokens when predicting fake news labels [18]. In contrast, SHAP explanations for BERT demonstrated the model's ability to consider broader contextual dependencies rather than isolated tokens and the token importance was more distributed [18].

These results help us better understand and trust automated fake news detection systems as they emphasize the importance of combining predictive performance with interpretability.

8. Limitations and Future Work

Although the analysis produced useful insights, it has a few limitations. Firstly, we used the WELFake for data which is a single benchmark dataset and therefore may limit the generalizability onto other news sources, domains and languages [20]. It is very possible that the model learning might not transfer well on other unseen data since it's trained on only one dataset and the characteristics of fake news can substantially differ across platforms and cultures [10]. Secondly, since transformer architecture based models rely on subword tokenization and therefore its classification decision might be influenced by the preprocessing pipeline which includes lemmatization and punctuation removal [16].

Explainability methods may be another limitation. Though LIME and SHAP provide local explanations for individual predictions [18]. Also, SHAP explanations may not efficiently scale to large datasets or real-time systems and can be computationally expensive [5]. Moreover, this analysis particularly focuses on token-level contributions and did not investigate discourse features that could further improve interpretability or look at higher-level linguistics.

Future work may extend this study by leveraging more advanced transformer architectures like RoBERTa or DeBERTa could be explored for performance improvements. (3) Additionally incorporating additional datasets and multilingual corpora in order to test the robustness across domains. With respect to explainability, we may be able to provide deeper insight into model trustworthiness by incorporating global explanation techniques and comparing human-centered evaluations [2]. Finally, hybrid approaches could be developed to balance performance with transparency that jointly optimize accuracy and interpretability in practical news detection applications.

9. Conclusion

This research performs fake news classification tasks using WELFake dataset and presents methodical evaluation of classical machine learning, deep learning and transformer architecture based models [20]. In the study the models were trained on both title and title and text combination, it demonstrates that in cases of dataset constraints the headline can serve as good indicators in cases on high complexity models, while modest performance improvements are observed with full-text representations. Amongst all the models evaluated, while classical TF-IDF models do perform well and remain competitive, BERT achieved the highest predictive performance [15]. The LSTM model became unstable when trained on short inputs. It proves that with enough data simpler models can still be relevant as an effective baseline whereas if there are data constraints high complexity transformer models might prove to be a more valuable asset.

Beyond performance evaluation, analysis uses LIME and SHAP to emphasize the importance of interpretability [18, 19]. The explainability analysis provided valuable insights into the decision making mechanism of different models and how they rely on lexical cues versus contextual understanding. This study addresses the growing societal impact of misinformation and contributes to the ongoing efforts to build more reliable, interpretable and trustworthy machine learning models.

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